

A new species of genus *Phytoecia* Dejean, 1835 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Israel

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Summary: *Phytoecia* (s. str.) *napolovi* sp. n. is described from Israel. The new species is similar to *Ph.* (s. str.) *shokhini* Kasatkin, 2010, but differs primarily in the absence of male coxal spines.

INTRODUCTION

Several general works were recently published on the Cerambycidae of the Near East fauna (Sama et al., 2002; Rejzek et al., 2003; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2000; Sama, Buse et al., 2010; Sama, Rapuzzi & Kairouz, 2010), but the Cerambycidae fauna of the region remains insufficiently known.

The discovery of a new remarkable *Phytoecia* (s. str.) is the important contribution to the study of the Cerambycidae of Israel.

***Phytoecia* (s. str.) *napolovi* sp. n.
(Figs.1-2)**

Type locality. Ein Zeitim, 2 km NE Zefat, E Halilaa, Israel.

Description. A single male known. Body totally black including abdominal apex as well as all legs and antennae, no metallic lustre observed.

Head covered with dense recumbent yellow pubescence anteriorly and laterally, which totally hides cuticle; vertex with a large yellow setose area.

Antennae surpassing elytral apex by two apical joints; 2nd antennal joint about 1.5.times longer than wide; 3rd joint as long as 4th and much longer than 1st; all other joints much shorter.

Prothorax cylindrical, about as wide anteriorly, as posteriorly; and about as long as wide; lateral thoracic areas with

narrow yellow setae lines; pronotum with a pair of poorly pronounced glabrous callosities; with wide central longitudinal hair stripe, with numerous pale erect setae; with distinct dense regular, partly confluent punctation, evenly convex, without any traces of longitudinal carina; ventral side of prothorax with dense yellow recumbent pubescence; scutellum transverse, also covered with dense yellow recumbent pubescence.

Elytra elongated, about 2.9 times longer than wide, with sides evenly converging posteriorly, not raised along suture; covered with pale grey regular pubescence; semierect setae relatively long anteriorly becoming short near middle and disappearing posteriorly; apex of each elytron truncated.

Legs partly (especially middle femora) with very fine yellow recumbent pubescence, not hiding cuticle; 3rd tarsal joint emarginated to about base; posterior coxae without spines.

Abdomen with regular grey recumbent pubescence; each abdominal segment with narrow yellow setae areas laterally; posterior margins of pygidium truncated, postpygidium slightly emarginated; last abdominal sternite slightly depressed apically and widely rounded.

Body length (from anterior margin of frons to elytral apices): 10.2 mm, body width (at humeri): 2.6 mm.

Type material. Holotype, male with the label: "Israel, E Halilaa, 2 km NE Zefat, Ein Zeitim, 15-17.03. 2006, A.Zamesov leg." – author's collection.

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to Alexander Napolov (Riga), who provided me with the specimen for description.

Remark. The new species resembles *Ph.* (s.str.) *shokhini* Kasatkin, 2010 in the body pubescence (**fig. 3**), but belongs to another group of species because of the absence of coxal spines. In addition, it completely lacks any traces of red (or reddish) cuticle, and the ventral side lacks dense recumbent yellow pubescence. *Ph. napolovi* **sp. n.** may belong to same species group as *Ph.* (s. str.) *annulipes* Mulsant & Rey, 1863 from south Turkey, which is characterized by partly red legs. It was recently redescribed and figured (Danilevsky, 2008.).

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Figs. 1-2. *Phytoecia* (s. str.) *napolovi* sp.n.:
1 – dorsal view, 2 – lateral view.
Fig. 3. *Phytoecia* (s. str.) *shokhini* Kasatkin, 2010:
male (paratype), Turkey, Tuncheli prov., 35km SE
Ovachik, 24-26.5.2009, Kasatkin & Shokhin leg. –
A.Miroshnikov collection.

REFERENCES

- Danilevsky M.L., 2008. Two new species of *Phytoecia* Dejean, 1835 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Armenia.- *Eversmannia*, Entomological research in the Russia and adjacent regions, N15-16: 6-16 + 1 plate.
- Kasatkin D.G., 2010. A new species of the genus *Phytoecia* Dejean 1835 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Eastern Turkey.- *Caucasian Entomological Bulletin*, 6(1): 73-74, plate 6.
- Rejzek M., Kadlec S. & Sama G., 2003. Contribution to the knowledge of Syrian Cerambycidae fauna (Coleoptera).- *Biocosme Mésogéen*, Nice, 20, 1: 7-50.
- Sama G., Buse J., Orbach E., Friedman A.L.L., Rittner O. & Chikatunov V., 2010. A new catalogue of the Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) of Israel with notes on their distribution and host plants.- *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 5 (1): 1-55.

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- Sama G., Katbeh-Bader A. & Miloud Mahdi D., 2002. A preliminary catalogue of the Cerambycidae of Jordan (Coleoptera).- Bulletin de la Société entomologique de France, 107 (5): 471-487.
- Sama G. & Rapuzzi P., 2000. Note préliminaire pour une faune des Cerambycidae du Liban (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae).- Lambillionea, 100, 1: 7-23.
- Sama G., Rapuzzi P. & Kairouz A., 2010. Catalogue commenté des Cerambycidae du Liban. An annotated catalogue of the Cerambycidae of Lebanon (Insecta Coleoptera Cerambycidae).- Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna, 30: 131-201.

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